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"Causes And Factors of Virtualization in Youth Life"

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ABSTRACT

Virtualization, which is developing rapidly today, is gaining a new meaning in the spirituality of every state, people, nation, or humanity. In the development of society, "just as every social phenomenon has its pros and cons, so does the process of virtualization. However, we must not forget that along with such achievements, virtualization also poses a spiritual threat to the national ideas, ideologies, beliefs and heritage of some peoples. This article focuses on this issue and the current issues of protecting young people from information attacks on the Internet and social networks.

Keywords:

Youth, Internet, Information, Globalization, Virtual Being, Media, Dependency, Information Attacks.

It is very difficult to imagine our lives today without the internet. The role of the global network in the lives of young people in particular is growing. The Internet has greatly facilitated the interaction and exchange of information between people living in different parts of the world. The Internet has great potential to influence the minds and emotions, mindsets, and behaviors of young people. The development of the Internet today has led to a dramatic increase in the scale and scope of ideological influence on young people.

Today, the Internet is one of the most important things in the daily lives of not only young people but members of all ages. But because of its popularity and uncontrollability, the concept of "popular culture" has come into our lives due to its correct and misuse, and today everyone, especially young people, use the Internet almost every day. The concept of a democratic state and a free civil society is unthinkable without information reforms.

It is known that the Internet, which appeared in the second half of the last century, has made a radical change in the field of information. Nowadays, the traditional media's ability to maintain its position in the age of information technology is largely dependent on the capabilities of the global network. In this regard, President Mirziyoyev stressed that "the widespread use of the Internet and other global information systems is especially important today in the process of forming a national information system. Achieving this will be crucial for the country's development in the 21st century," he said. Of course, these sources of information are important in broadening the worldview and increasing the knowledge of the younger generation. While not denying the positive aspects of the media and social media, it should also be noted that it has the potential to have an ineffective, negative impact on young people.

Given that young people are not yet fully immune to destructive, destructive ideas, and

that they are very quick to believe what they hear or read, this is a global issue that needs a lot of attention. It should be noted that subversive information spread on the Internet can sometimes achieve goals that cannot be achieved through military action. It should not be forgotten that such information attacks are aimed at deliberately changing the spiritual, moral, psychological worldview, political views and beliefs of young people. One of the main reasons for this is the proliferation of TV, radio, audio, video and multimedia products that promote aggression, information on the Internet, computer games, and their distribution in various ways. All of them are an effective means of informational and psychological influence on the mental and psycho-emotional state of children and young people.

The Internet has great potential to influence the minds and emotions, mindsets, and behaviors of young people. The development of the Internet today has led to a dramatic increase in the scale and scope of ideological influence on young people. The role of the religious factor in conquering hearts by mastering this means of development is high. That is why various religious extremist and terrorist groups are using the Internet as the most effective tool to promote their ideas. At the same time, the main task of religious extremist movements is to use modern information communications to achieve their goals, to propagate in different languages via the Internet and to create virtual communities based on a well-developed strategy. Today, for example, several major terrorist organizations are actively recruiting people to their ranks, mainly between the ages of 17-35, through social media. In order to further increase the effectiveness of the psychological impact, the pages of social network members, photos, comments and comments, as well as the topics of conversation are carefully studied, and on this basis, the "targeted" person can find materials on the Internet Facebook, Odnoklassniki, It is sent and interacted with via social networks (written message, text, photo, sticker pictures, audio-video clip) with a wide audience, such as VKontakte, Telegram,

Twitter, WhatsApp. The growing popularity of such fanatical forums among young people and the fact that they issue all sorts of destructive "fatwas" show how serious the problem is. Because the majority of the world's population is young. Young people are a great force. What is imprinted in their emerging minds is sealed like a pattern carved in stone. That's why radical movements are trying to trap young people. Their confidence, energy and enthusiasm will help them achieve their goals. Unfortunately, such hateful forces seek to attract people, especially young people, who are far from science and enlightenment, and do not know the true meaning of pure religious concepts, and misuse the concepts of "jihad", "takfir", "martyrdom" and "migration" through social media. He is trying to leave his homeland with the interpretation of There is also widespread propaganda by some individuals of deliberately unfounded information that contradicts the essence of Islam, religious messages of unknown origin, or photos and videos that frighten people. At the same time, the fact that some young people believe in unsubstantiated information and data that contradicts our national and religious values through the media, without a clear source, and blindly accept it without thinking, has even more serious consequences. produces.

As information has become a commodity today, everyone needs to cultivate a culture of consumption. Young people need to have the knowledge and skills to protect personal information and be able to protect themselves from the negative information they use. The culture of information consumption, in the broadest sense, refers to a system of knowledge, skills, and competencies from the flow of information that serves to receive, sort, understand, and interpret information that serves human interests, maturity, and the development of society.

In the younger generation, these aspects should be formed and decided in such a way that they can choose the information that will serve the national interest and contribute to its development in the virtual space. Young people with a culture of information

consumption are not exposed to negative and biased information, as they develop a strong ideological immunity to such information.

It is necessary to learn to live vigilantly, vigilantly and vigilantly against ideological threats, and to pay special attention to the formation of one-sided and false perceptions about the cruel games of a complex and dangerous life. To do this, people need a healthy lifestyle, respect for national and universal values - respect, self-confidence and confidence in the future. According to others, globalization poses a great danger not in the economic sphere but in the religious sphere, because globalism and information are combined with the propaganda of atheism at a time when they are secular in nature. Again, in the eyes of others, globalization undermines the nation and national identity. Cultural values, including religious values, and lifestyles are also at risk. For scientists and politicians who tend to take such an approach, striving to preserve cultural identity is a key goal. Because now the majority of Internet users are young people. Young people are the future of the nation and the state. It should be noted that the period requires the development of a program aimed at developing a healthy attitude of young people to globalization. It must be clear to all of us that where indifference and indifference prevail, spirituality becomes the weakest and weakest point, and wherever vigilance and zeal prevail, spirituality becomes a powerful force.

Especially in the international arena today, different political forces have their own national and strategic. In order to achieve their plans, it is important to understand the essence and goals of long-term policy in a timely manner.

The idea that "whoever has the information, owns the world" is widely accepted today. Therefore, today the formation of skills in the rational use of the opportunities of the information world in young people is of vital practical importance. Therefore, the socio-political processes taking place in different regions and territories of the world, the deepening of the sense of conflict, the organization of spiritual and educational work against all kinds of threats on the basis of

modern requirements, especially in this regard. we must mobilize all our forces and capabilities to protect the younger generation, in a word, our family, which is sacred to each of us, from the influence of foreign ideas under the guise of religion. As President Mirziyoyev noted, "Today, when the world is rapidly changing and various new threats and dangers are emerging that threaten the stability and sustainable development of peoples, spirituality and enlightenment, moral education, youth education, maturity It is more important than ever to focus on

We, the youth, must demonstrate our knowledge and potential for the development of our Motherland, achieve great success and innovate in all areas, and for this we must mobilize our skills and abilities in this direction. At the same time, through the effective use of information technology, the proper use of the media and the Internet, we must acquire the necessary and necessary knowledge, not to follow other foreign ideas and selflessly serve the development of the country and be a worthy child. we need to get la. Because the future of our country is in the hands of our youth. Only then will we be able to achieve our goal and raise our country to the heights and make it the highest in the world community. If our hearts are filled with love for the Motherland, noble ideas and goals, our country will surely develop and prosper.

As the President said, in order to prevent the information crisis, we must fight against ideology, against ideology, against ignorance, against enlightenment. May the spiritual and moral purity in the hearts of our young people serve the cause of good.

List of used literature:

1. Mirziyoev.Sh.M. We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level. Volume 1 -T .: Uzbekistan, 2018. Pages 29-30.
2. Mirziyoev.Sh.M. Liberalization of our society, deepening of reforms, raising our morale and raising the living standards of our people are the criteria

- and goal of all our work. T. 15. -T .: Uzbekistan. 2017. -326 b.
3. Safoeva. S. The impact of globalization on social life. // Political, philosophical and legal issues of democratization of society in the process of globalization. - Tashkent: Philosophy and Law Publishing House, 2006, 27 pages.
 4. Kuchkarov. V. National Awareness and Sustainable Development T .: Academy, 2013 p.67
 5. Zokirov B. Western civilization: signs of crisis // Tafakkur, 2007. 2o2. - 23 b.